

General theory of orientation
- the visual vertical

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Chapter 1

The resultant acceleration

We want to determine the direction of the resultant acceleration (with that the visual vertical) general.

1.1 Case I

First we view the situation at **one** general revolution solid (planet) with an observer on the surface. The revolution solid rotates with the angular velocity $\vec{\omega}(t)$. t shall be the time. We search the total acceleration $\vec{b}_{ges}(t)$, acting to the observer on the revolution solid. The observer shall have the position $\vec{p}$ on the revolution solid.

It is $r, h_j \geq 0$. $j \in 1, 2$

$j = 1$ = north part

$j = 2$ = south part

The revolution solid has the form of the function $h_j(r, t)$. h_1 and h_2 can be different. We obtain for the latitude:

$$\tan \alpha_j = \frac{(-1)^{j-1} \cdot h_j}{r}$$

$\varphi(t)$ is the longitude. Then we get:

$$\vec{p} = \begin{pmatrix} r \cos \varphi \\ r \sin \varphi \\ (-1)^{j-1} \cdot h_j \end{pmatrix}$$

The revolution solid shall have a translation motion $\vec{s}(t)$ relative to a general coordinate system. First we neglect the gravitational forces of other bodies. According to Budo [2], § 14, p.74, equation (16) it is valid for the total acceleration:

$$\vec{b}_{ges}(t) = \vec{g}(\vec{p}, t) - \ddot{\vec{s}} - \vec{\omega} \times (\vec{\omega} \times \vec{p}) - \dot{\vec{\omega}} \times \vec{p} - 2 \cdot (\vec{\omega} \times \dot{\vec{p}})$$

$\vec{g}(\vec{p}, t)$ is the gravitational acceleration of the revolution solid at $\vec{p}$. This gravitational acceleration can be different:

1) Newton's gravitation law:

$$\vec{g}(\vec{p}, t) = \frac{G \cdot M(t)}{|\vec{p}|^2} \cdot \frac{-\vec{p}}{|\vec{p}|}$$

G is the gravitational constant and $M(t)$ the mass of the revolution solid. $|\cdot|$ is the stathm of a vector. This law is valid for spheres or similar revolution solids.

2) central field:

$$\vec{g}(\vec{p}, t) = f(|\vec{p}|, M(t), t) \cdot \frac{-\vec{p}}{|\vec{p}|}$$

3): At complicated gravitational fields $\vec{g}(\vec{p}, t)$ must be calculated with the gravitation theory. The revolution ellipsoid belongs to this case.

Normal vectors

Now we define the normal vectors on the revolution solid's surface. We need the gradient $S(r) := \frac{\partial h_j(r, t)}{\partial r}$:

Then we get for the exterior normal vector:

$$\vec{n} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi \\ \sin \varphi \\ (-1)^{j-1} \cdot \frac{1}{|S|} \end{pmatrix}$$

$|\cdot| = \text{stathm}$

Now we work with the gravitational force, if m is the observer's mass: This force is $\vec{F} = m \cdot \vec{g}(\vec{p}, t)$ at constant observer's mass and $\vec{F} \approx m(t) \cdot \vec{g}(\vec{p}, t)$, if $m(t)$ is not constant and changes only slowly.

The total force is $\vec{F}_{ges} = m \cdot \vec{b}_{ges}(t)$ at constant observer's mass and $\vec{F}_{ges} \approx m(t) \cdot \vec{b}_{ges}(t)$ at temporal slow changing observer's mass.

If v is the velocity, for the force it is valid in general:

$$F = \frac{d(m \cdot v)}{dt} = m \cdot \dot{v} + \dot{m} \cdot v$$

The approximations are only valid, if $\dot{m} \cdot v \ll m \cdot \dot{v}$. The visual vertical shows in direction of the total force $\vec{F}_{ges}$, if all forces that are taken apart changes only slowly. An uncharged pendulum also turns in the direction of $\vec{F}_{ges}$.

Now we introduce the angle of deviation $\beta = \angle(\vec{F}, \vec{F}_{ges})$. We need the scalar product:

$$\cos \beta = \frac{\vec{F} \cdot \vec{F}_{ges}}{|\vec{F}| \cdot |\vec{F}_{ges}|} = \frac{\vec{g}(\vec{p}, t) \cdot \vec{b}_{ges}(t)}{|\vec{g}(\vec{p}, t)| \cdot |\vec{b}_{ges}(t)|}$$

We note that the second term is only approximately valid at slow changing observer's mass m .

Now we look at the pitch angle $\gamma = \angle(-\vec{n}, \vec{F}_{ges})$ on the surface:

We conclude with the scalar product again:

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{-\vec{n} \cdot \vec{F}_{ges}}{|\vec{n}| \cdot |\vec{F}_{ges}|} = \frac{-\vec{n} \cdot \vec{b}_{ges}(t)}{|\vec{n}| \cdot |\vec{b}_{ges}(t)|}$$

Here the second term is only approximately valid at slow changing observer's mass.

1.2 Case II

Now we consider the following situation: A spaceship has the motion $\vec{s}(t)$ in a general coordinate system.

n bodies (planets) shall be there. $\vec{s}_i(t)$ is the motion of the i . body in the general coordinate system. We denote with $\vec{g}_i$ the gravitational acceleration of the i . body. We assume that the spaceship is small compared to the n bodies. Then we don't need the spaceship's own gravitation. The observer has perhaps the motion $\vec{a}(t)$ in spaceship.

$M_i = M_i(t)$ = mass of i . body
 $\vec{r} = \vec{s} + \vec{a}$ = total motion of the observer

To the gravitational fields of the n bodies we have the following cases:

1) Newton's gravitation law:

$$\vec{g}_i = \frac{GM_i}{|\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i|^2} \cdot \frac{\vec{s}_i - \vec{r}}{|\vec{s}_i - \vec{r}|}$$

Then the i . body must be a ball or similar to a ball.

2) central field:

$$\vec{g}_i = f(|\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i|, M_i, t) \cdot \frac{\vec{s}_i - \vec{r}}{|\vec{s}_i - \vec{r}|}$$

3): At complicated gravitational fields the calculation of $\vec{g}_i = \vec{g}_i(\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i, t)$ must be done with the gravitation theory.

Approximately we can insert $\vec{s}$ instead of $\vec{r}$, because of $|\vec{a}| \ll |\vec{s} - \vec{s}_i| \approx |\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i|$ in general. This can be determined easier.

If the observer in spaceship does not move, then $\vec{a}(t) = 0$.

Now we calculate the total acceleration:

$$\vec{b}_{ges} = \sum_{i=1}^n \vec{g}_i(\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i, t) - \ddot{\vec{r}} \quad (1.1)$$

$\vec{t} = -\ddot{\vec{r}}$ is the inertia vector.

At slow rotation of the spaceship the equation (1) is valid approximately.

Now we turn to the forces:

If the observer's mass is constant, we have $\vec{F}_{ges} = m \cdot \vec{b}_{ges}$ as total force and $\vec{F}_i = m \cdot \vec{g}_i$ as gravitational force of the i . body. At temporal slow changing observer's mass both equation are valid approximately.

We introduce the angle of deviation $\beta_i = \angle(\vec{F}_{ges}, \vec{F}_i)$. We use the scalar product:

$$\cos \beta_i = \frac{\vec{F}_{ges} \cdot \vec{F}_i}{|\vec{F}_{ges}| \cdot |\vec{F}_i|}$$

An uncharged pendulum turns in direction of $\vec{F}_{ges}$. But the visual vertical cannot show in the direction of $\vec{F}_{ges}$. This is valid especially at fast changing of motion.

An equivalent assertion about $\vec{b}_{ges}$

If the spaceship has a inertial flight, it is valid because of the n-body-problem:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \vec{g}_i(\vec{s} - \vec{s}_i, t) = \ddot{\vec{s}}(t) \quad (1.2)$$

If we insert $\vec{r} = \vec{s} + \vec{a}$, we get with equation (1):

$$\vec{b}_{ges}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n \vec{g}_i(\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i, t) - \ddot{\vec{s}} - \ddot{\vec{a}}$$

Now we use equation (2):

$$= \sum_{i=1}^n \vec{g}_i(\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i, t) - \sum_{i=1}^n \vec{g}_i(\vec{s} - \vec{s}_i, t) - \ddot{\vec{a}}$$

At last we obtain:

$$\vec{b}_{ges} = \sum_{i=1}^n (\vec{g}_i(\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i, t) - \vec{g}_i(\vec{s} - \vec{s}_i, t)) - \ddot{\vec{a}} \quad (1.3)$$

$\vec{g}_i(\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i, t) - \vec{g}_i(\vec{s} - \vec{s}_i, t)$ is the gravitational acceleration of the i.body to the observer in spaceship

We had viewed the inertial spaceship. If the space ship has an acceleration $\vec{b}^*(t)$, instead of equation (2), we need the following equation to the n-body problem:

$$\ddot{\vec{s}} = \vec{b}^*(t) + \sum_{i=1}^n \vec{g}_i(\vec{s} - \vec{s}_i, t) \quad (1.4)$$

With equation (1) and $\vec{r} = \vec{s} + \vec{a}$ it is:

$$\vec{b}_{ges} = \sum_{i=1}^n \vec{g}_i(\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i, t) - \ddot{\vec{s}} - \ddot{\vec{a}}$$

Now we use equation (4):

$$\vec{b}_{ges} = \sum_{i=1}^n \vec{g}_i(\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i, t) - \sum_{i=1}^n \vec{g}_i(\vec{s} - \vec{s}_i, t) - \vec{b}^* - \ddot{\vec{a}}$$

At last it follows:

$$\vec{b}_{ges}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n (\vec{g}_i(\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i, t) - \vec{g}_i(\vec{s} - \vec{s}_i, t)) - \vec{b}^*(t) - \ddot{\vec{a}} \quad (1.5)$$

Now we have a formula for the spaceship with drive. In a spaceship that is very small compared to planets, will be:

$$\vec{g}_i(\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i, t) \approx \vec{g}_i(\vec{s} - \vec{s}_i, t)$$

for $i \in 1, \dots, n$. With that we get the equation:

$$\vec{b}_{ges}(t) \approx -\vec{b}^*(t) - \ddot{\vec{a}} \quad (1.6)$$

In a spaceship this formula is practical.

During the most part of the time of flight we have $\vec{b}^* = 0$, but not during starting and landing. At $\vec{b}^* = 0$ the visual vertical in general does not show in the direction of $\vec{b}_{ges}$. In this case the astronauts are weightless in a spaceship. First the astronauts have no orientation. If the angular velocity of the space ship is small, the astronauts sometimes manage after some time to choose the visual vertical themselves. To this case see Calvin [3], Chapter 7, book 1.

1.3 Case III

Now the observer shall be on a revolution solid (planet). We take into consideration the gravitational forces of n other bodies.

$\vec{g}_i$ = gravitational acceleration of the i.body

$\vec{s}_i$ = position of centre of gravity of the i. body

$\vec{g}$ = gravitational acceleration of the revolution solid

$\vec{s}$ = revolution solid's midpoint position

$M(t)$ = mass of the revolution solid

$M_i(t)$ = mass of the i.body

$\vec{s}_i, \vec{s}$ are relative to the general coordinate system.

It is $r, h_j \geq 0 \quad j \in 1, 2$

$j = 1 =$ north part
 $j = 2 =$ south part

The observer has the position $\vec{p}$ relative to the revolution solid's coordinate-system. The origin of this coordinate system is the geometrical midpoint of the revolution solid. For the latitude we obtain:

$$\tan \alpha_j = \frac{(-1)^{j-1} \cdot h_j}{r}$$

The observer shall be on longitude $\varphi(t_0)$. $h_j(r, t)$ is the revolution solid's function with $j=1$ for the north part and $j=2$ for the south part. Then we can express the position $\vec{p}$ of the observer:

$$\vec{p} = \begin{pmatrix} r \cos \varphi \\ r \sin \varphi \\ (-1)^{j-1} \cdot h_j \end{pmatrix} \quad w = |\vec{w}| \quad \vec{w}(t) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ w(t) \end{pmatrix}$$

and

$$\varphi(t) = \varphi(t_0) + \int_{t_0}^t w(\bar{t}) d\bar{t}$$

$\vec{g}(\vec{p}, t)$ is the gravitational acceleration of the revolution solid at $\vec{p}$. This gravitational acceleration can be different:

1) Newton's gravitational law:

$$\vec{g}(\vec{p}, t) = \frac{G \cdot M(t)}{|\vec{p}|^2} \cdot \frac{-\vec{p}}{|\vec{p}|}$$

G is the gravitational constant and $M(t)$ the mass of the revolution solid. $|\cdot|$ is the stathm of a vector. This law is valid to ball or to revolution solids that are similar to ball.

2) central field:

$$\vec{g}(\vec{p}, t) = f(|\vec{p}|, M(t), t) \cdot \frac{-\vec{p}}{|\vec{p}|}$$

3): At complicated gravitational fields $\vec{g}(\vec{p}, t)$ must be determined with the gravitational theory. The revolution ellipsoids belong to this case.

$\vec{r} = \vec{s} + \vec{p}$ = total motion of the observer in general
coordinate system

The gravitational fields of the n bodies can be different:

1) Newton's law of gravitation:

$$\vec{g}_i = \frac{GM_i}{|\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i|^2} \cdot \frac{\vec{s}_i - \vec{r}}{|\vec{s}_i - \vec{r}|}$$

Then the i . body must be a ball or similar to a ball.

2) central field:

$$\vec{g}_i = f(|\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i|, M_i, t) \cdot \frac{\vec{s}_i - \vec{r}}{|\vec{s}_i - \vec{r}|}$$

3): At complicated gravitational fields the calculation of $\vec{g}_i = \vec{g}_i(\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i, t)$ must be done with the gravitational theory.

Now we turn to the total acceleration:

$$\vec{b}_{ges}(t) = \vec{g}(\vec{p}, t) + \sum_{i=1}^n \vec{g}_i(\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i, t) - \ddot{\vec{r}} \quad (1.7)$$

$\vec{t} = -\ddot{\vec{r}}$ is the inertial vector.

Now we are going to look at the gravitational force of the revolution solid. m is the observer's mass: This force is $\vec{F} = m \cdot \vec{g}(\vec{p}, t)$ at constant observer's mass and $\vec{F} \approx m(t) \cdot \vec{g}(\vec{p}, t)$, if $m(t)$ is not constant and changes only slowly.

The total force can be written as $\vec{F}_{ges} = m \cdot \vec{b}_{ges}(t)$ at constant observer's mass and $\vec{F}_{ges} \approx m(t) \cdot \vec{b}_{ges}(t)$ at temporal slowly changing observer's mass.

If v is the velocity, then for the force it is valid in general:

$$F = \frac{d(m \cdot v)}{dt} = m \cdot \dot{v} + \dot{m} \cdot v$$

The approximations are only valid, if $\dot{m} \cdot v \ll m \cdot \dot{v}$. The visual vertical shows approximately in the direction of total force $\vec{F}_{ges}$, if all forces changes only slowly. The angular velocity w must be small. An uncharged pendulum turns in the direction of $\vec{F}_{ges}$. In outer space are in general only weak electric fields, with that such pendulums are hardly influenced.

Now we introduce the angle of deviation $\beta = \angle(\vec{F}, \vec{F}_{ges})$. We need the scalar product:

$$\cos \beta = \frac{\vec{F} \cdot \vec{F}_{ges}}{|\vec{F}| \cdot |\vec{F}_{ges}|} = \frac{\vec{g}(\vec{p}, t) \cdot \vec{b}_{ges}(t)}{|\vec{g}(\vec{p}, t)| \cdot |\vec{b}_{ges}(t)|}$$

The second formula is only approximately valid at slow temporal changing observer's mass m .

Normal vectors

Now we calculate the normal vectors on the revolution solid's surface. We need the gradient $S(r) := \frac{\partial h_j(r, t)}{\partial r}$.

Then we obtain for the exterior normal vector:

$$\vec{n} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi \\ \sin \varphi \\ (-1)^{j-1} \cdot \frac{1}{|S|} \end{pmatrix}$$

$|\cdot|$ = absolute value

Now we view the pitch angle $\gamma = \angle(-\vec{n}, \vec{F}_{ges})$ at the surface:

We again conclude with the scalar product:

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{-\vec{n} \cdot \vec{F}_{ges}}{|\vec{n}| \cdot |\vec{F}_{ges}|} = \frac{-\vec{n} \cdot \vec{b}_{ges}(t)}{|\vec{n}| \cdot |\vec{b}_{ges}(t)|}$$

The second formula is only valid approximately at temporal slow changing observer's mass.

The case I is a special case of case III. But in case I is $\vec{w}(t) \in R^3$ in case III it must be:

$$\vec{w}(t) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ w(t) \end{pmatrix}$$

A equivalent statement about $\vec{b}_{ges}$

Here we need the equation of the n-body-problem:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \vec{g}_i(\vec{s} - \vec{s}_i, t) = \ddot{\vec{s}}(t) \quad (1.8)$$

Now we insert in equation (7) $\vec{r} = \vec{s} + \vec{p}$:

$$\vec{b}_{ges} = \vec{g}(\vec{p}, t) + \sum_{i=1}^n \vec{g}_i(\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i, t) - \ddot{\vec{s}} - \ddot{\vec{p}}$$

We use equation (8):

$$\vec{b}_{ges} = \vec{g}(\vec{p}, t) + \sum_{i=1}^n \vec{g}_i(\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i, t) - \sum_{i=1}^n \vec{g}_i(\vec{s} - \vec{s}_i, t) - \ddot{\vec{p}}$$

We get as result:

$$\vec{b}_{ges}(t) = \vec{g}(\vec{p}, t) - \ddot{\vec{p}} + \sum_{i=1}^n (\vec{g}_i(\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i, t) - \vec{g}_i(\vec{s} - \vec{s}_i, t)) \quad (1.9)$$

$\vec{g}_i(\vec{r} - \vec{s}_i, t) - \vec{g}_i(\vec{s} - \vec{s}_i, t)$ is the gravitational acceleration of the i.body to the observer on the revolution solid.

angle of height over the horizon of the revolution solid

Now we want to know, which angle of height a body has with the position $\vec{r}_A(t)$ over the horizon of the revolution solid's surface.

$\vec{r}_A(t)$ = Motion of the body in general coordinate system, which angle of height over the horizon shall be calculated.

$\vec{r}(t)$ is the position of the observer. $\alpha_h > 0$ means the body is over the horizon, during at $\alpha_h < 0$ the body is under the horizon.

We can determine the angle of height over the horizon with:

$$\alpha_h = 90^\circ - \angle(\vec{r}_A - \vec{r}, \vec{n})$$

It follows:

$$\alpha_h = 90^\circ - \arccos\left(\frac{(\vec{r}_A - \vec{r}) \cdot \vec{n}}{|\vec{r}_A - \vec{r}| \cdot |\vec{n}|}\right)$$

α_h is a function of the time.

1.4 Case II and Case III

Now we get to know a further interesting quantity. We denote the height angle to $\vec{F}_{ges}$ as δ . We have:

$\vec{r}(t)$ = position of the observer

$\vec{r}_A(t)$ = Motion of the body in general coordinate system. From this body the height angle shall be calculated.

$$\delta + 90^\circ = \angle(\vec{F}_{ges}, (\vec{r}_A - \vec{r}))$$

with that:

$$\cos(\delta + 90^\circ) = \frac{\vec{F}_{ges} \cdot (\vec{r}_A - \vec{r})}{|\vec{F}_{ges}| \cdot |\vec{r}_A - \vec{r}|}$$

At last we get:

$$\delta = \arccos \left(\frac{\vec{F}_{ges}(t) \cdot (\vec{r}_A(t) - \vec{r}(t))}{|\vec{F}_{ges}(t)| \cdot |\vec{r}_A(t) - \vec{r}(t)|} \right) - 90^\circ$$

$$-90^\circ \leq \delta \leq 90^\circ$$

Chapter 2

The determination of circle orbits from the angular velocity

At Case III we must assume $\vec{w} = (0, 0, w)$. Now it shall be $\vec{w}$ general in R^3 . According to Budo [2], §14, p. 72. equation (8) it is valid:

$$\vec{v} = \vec{w} \times \vec{r}_1$$

It is:

$\vec{w}$ = angular velocity

$\vec{v}$ = velocity

$\vec{r}_1(t)$ = motion of the orbit (circle orbit)

t, t_0 = time, start time

First we assume that the midpoint of the circle orbit is the origin. Later we make a corresponding shift.

At circular motion is $\vec{r}_1$ perpendicular to $\vec{w}$. It follows $\vec{r}_1 \cdot \vec{w} = 0$.

$$\vec{v} = \vec{w} \times \vec{r}_1 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \vec{v} \times \vec{r}_1 = (\vec{w} \times \vec{r}_1) \times \vec{r}_1$$

We obtain with the expansion theorem:

$$\vec{v} \times \vec{r}_1 = (\vec{w} \cdot \vec{r}_1) \cdot \vec{r}_1 - (\vec{r}_1 \cdot \vec{r}_1) \cdot \vec{w}$$

The first scalar product is zero, because of the circular motion. With that we get:

$$\vec{v} \times \vec{r}_1 = -\vec{r}_1^2 \cdot \vec{w} \quad \vec{v} = \dot{\vec{r}}_1$$

The circle's radius is known. It follows:

$$\vec{r}_1 \times \dot{\vec{r}}_1 = r_1^2 \cdot \vec{w} \quad r_1^2 := \vec{r}_1^2 \quad (2.1)$$

The initial condition $\vec{r}(t_0)$ is known. Because of the circular motion we can put $r_1^2 = \vec{r}_1(t_0)^2$ equal to a constant c . We have a initial-value problem with 3 usual differential equations. $\vec{r}_1(t)$ is searched.

Now we view the following figure:

Now we shift the origin to the geometrical midpoint of the revolution solid. Then for the searched motion we have:

$$\vec{r}(t) = h(r_1) \cdot \frac{\vec{w}}{|\vec{w}|} + \vec{r}_1(t)$$

$\vec{r}(t)$ is the searched motion in Case III from the previous chapter. $h(r)$ denotes again the revolution solid's function (see previous chapter). If we know $\vec{r}_1(t)$, we can also determine $\vec{r}$. With that we look at the differential equation system $\vec{r}_1 \times \dot{\vec{r}}_1 = c \cdot \vec{w}$ with $c = \vec{r}_1(t_0)^2$. We introduce $\vec{w} = (w_1, w_2, w_3)$ and $\vec{r}_1 = (x, y, z)$. We can write the system in the following form:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{z} \end{pmatrix} = c \cdot \begin{pmatrix} w_1 \\ w_2 \\ w_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

We get:

$$\begin{aligned} y\dot{z} - z\dot{y} &= cw_1 \\ z\dot{x} - x\dot{z} &= cw_2 \\ x\dot{y} - y\dot{x} &= cw_3 \end{aligned}$$

This is a non linear differential equation system of first order. The system can be solved explicitly to $\hat{x}, \hat{y}, \hat{z}$.

We can obtain an exact solution perhaps only with power series or still more general series expansion. $\vec{w}$ can be temporal constant or not constant. Further information are in Kamke [5] A, §2, chapter 6.3, p.38.

Chapter 3

Transformation to the surface's coordinate system

3.1 The general revolution solid

We will see how to calculate the spherical coordinates an arbitrary vector $\vec{r} \in R^3$ relative to a surface's coordinate system.

We introduce the general revolution solid:

It is $r, h_j \geq 0$. $j \in 1, 2$

$j = 1$ = north part

$j = 2$ = south part

The revolution solid has the form of the function $h_j(r, t)$. h_1 and h_2 can be different. For the latitude we get:

$$\tan \alpha_j = \frac{(-1)^{j-1} \cdot h_j}{r}$$

$\varphi(t)$ is the longitude. Then we obtain:(see chapter 1)

$$\vec{p} = \begin{pmatrix} r \cos \varphi \\ r \sin \varphi \\ (-1)^{j-1} \cdot h_j \end{pmatrix}$$

Normal vectors

We calculate the normal vectors on the revolution solid's surface. We need the gradient $S(r) := \frac{\partial h_j(r, t)}{\partial r}$:

Then we get for the exterior normal vector:

$$\vec{n} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi \\ \sin \varphi \\ (-1)^{j-1} \cdot \frac{1}{|S|} \end{pmatrix}$$

$|\cdot|$ is the stathm. Now we search the tangent vector in northern direction:

$\vec{T}_j$ = tangent vector in northern direction
 $j = 1$ = north part
 $j = 2$ = south part

For the north part we have:

$$\vec{T}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\varphi + 180^\circ) \\ \sin(\varphi + 180^\circ) \\ |S| \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\cos \varphi \\ -\sin \varphi \\ |S| \end{pmatrix}$$

On the south part:

$$\vec{T}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi \\ \sin \varphi \\ |S| \end{pmatrix}$$

We calculate:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{n} \cdot \vec{T}_1 &= \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi \\ \sin \varphi \\ (-1)^{1-1} \cdot \frac{1}{|S|} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} -\cos \varphi \\ -\sin \varphi \\ |S| \end{pmatrix} \\ &= -\cos^2 \varphi - \sin^2 \varphi + 1 = 0 \end{aligned}$$

because of $\sin^2 \varphi + \cos^2 \varphi = 1$. With that $\vec{T}_1$ is perpendicular to $\vec{n}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{n} \cdot \vec{T}_2 &= \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi \\ \sin \varphi \\ (-1)^{2-1} \cdot \frac{1}{|S|} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi \\ \sin \varphi \\ |S| \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \cos^2 \varphi + \sin^2 \varphi - 1 = 0 \end{aligned}$$

That means: $\vec{T}_2$ is perpendicular to $\vec{n}$.

$\vec{T}$ always shows on both parts ($j = 1, 2$) of the revolution solid in northern direction. Instead of $\vec{T}_1$ respectively $\vec{T}_2$ we most denote the tangent vector from now on only with $\vec{T}$.

In addition we must introduce the tangent vector $\vec{T}_o$ in eastern direction:

$$0 \leq \varphi \leq 90^\circ$$

$$x = -\cos(90^\circ - \varphi) \quad y = \sin(90^\circ - \varphi) \quad z = 0$$

$$270^\circ \leq \varphi \leq 360^\circ$$

$$x = \cos(\varphi - 270^\circ) \quad y = \sin(\varphi - 270^\circ) \quad z = 0$$

$$90^\circ \leq \varphi \leq 180^\circ$$

$$x = -\cos(\varphi - 90^\circ) \quad y = -\sin(\varphi - 90^\circ) \quad z = 0$$

$$180^\circ \leq \varphi \leq 270^\circ$$

$$x = \cos(270^\circ - \varphi) \quad y = -\sin(270^\circ - \varphi) \quad z = 0$$

With that we follow:

$0 \leq \varphi \leq 90^\circ$	$x = -\sin \varphi$	$y = \cos \varphi$
$90^\circ \leq \varphi \leq 180^\circ$	$x = -\sin \varphi$	$y = \cos \varphi$
$180^\circ \leq \varphi \leq 270^\circ$	$x = -\sin \varphi$	$y = \cos \varphi$

$$270^\circ \leq \varphi \leq 360^\circ \quad x = -\sin \varphi \quad y = \cos \varphi$$

With that for the tangent vector in eastern direction we directly get:

$$\vec{T}_o = \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \varphi \\ \cos \varphi \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{for} \quad 0 \leq \varphi \leq 360^\circ$$

Now we calculate:

$$\vec{T}_o \cdot \vec{T}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \varphi \\ \cos \varphi \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} -\cos \varphi \\ -\sin \varphi \\ |S| \end{pmatrix} = 0$$

$$\vec{T}_o \cdot \vec{T}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \varphi \\ \cos \varphi \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi \\ \sin \varphi \\ |S| \end{pmatrix} = 0$$

$\vec{T}_o$ is perpendicular to $\vec{T}_1$ and $\vec{T}_2$, with that also to $\vec{T}$.

Now we calculate:

$$\vec{T}_o \cdot \vec{n} = \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \varphi \\ \cos \varphi \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi \\ \sin \varphi \\ (-1)^{j-1} \cdot \frac{1}{|S|} \end{pmatrix} = 0$$

With that $\vec{T}_o$ is perpendicular to the normal vector $\vec{n}$.

Now we turn to the surface's coordinate system, which has the origin $\vec{p}$. We know that:

$$\vec{p} = \begin{pmatrix} r \cos \varphi \\ r \sin \varphi \\ (-1)^{j-1} \cdot h_j \end{pmatrix}$$

First we calculate the height angle β of a arbitrary vector $\vec{r} \in R^3$ relative to the surface's coordinate system of $\vec{p}$:

$$\beta = 90^\circ - \angle(\vec{n}, \vec{r}) \quad \beta \in [-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$$

With that it is $\angle(\vec{n}, \vec{r}) = 90^\circ - \beta$. Now we use the scalar product:

$$\frac{\vec{n} \cdot \vec{r}}{|\vec{n}| \cdot |\vec{r}|} = \cos(90^\circ - \beta) = \sin \beta$$

We have determined the height angle β . We need this angle to calculate the longitude angle γ . This is the longitude angle of $\vec{r}$ relative to the surface's coordinate system of $\vec{p}$. Another possibility to express $\vec{T}$ is:

$$\vec{T} := \begin{pmatrix} (-1)^j \cdot \cos \varphi \\ (-1)^j \cdot \sin \varphi \\ |S| \end{pmatrix}$$

$j = 1$ is for the north part and $j = 2$ for the south part.

N = north S = south O = east W = west

To determine γ , we need γ_1 and γ_2 . These two angles can be calculated with the scalar product of the tangent vectors and the projection $\vec{r}_p$ of $\vec{r}$ relative to the tangent plane. First we determine this projection $\vec{r}_p$, then we calculate γ_1 and γ_2 and then we can conclude to γ . We look at the following figure:

Then we can use the following equation:

$$\vec{r}_p = \lambda \cdot \vec{T} + \mu \cdot \vec{T}_o \quad (3.1)$$

We obtain the second equation from the scalar product and $\angle(\vec{r}_p, \vec{r}) = |\beta|$. The absolute value is here, because $\beta < 0$ is possible, too.

$$\vec{r}_p \cdot \vec{r} = |\vec{r}_p| \cdot |\vec{r}| \cdot \cos |\beta| \quad (3.2)$$

$\vec{r}$ is known, and β is calculated before. Further we have a third equation:

$$|\vec{r}| \cdot \cos |\beta| = |\vec{r}_p| \quad (3.3)$$

We have 5 equations with the unknowns λ, μ and $\vec{r}_p$. In general this is sufficient to determine $\vec{r}_p$.

$\gamma_1 := \angle(\vec{r}_p, \vec{T})$ and $\gamma_2 := \angle(\vec{r}_p, \vec{T}_o)$, with that it is valid:

$$\cos \gamma_1 = \frac{\vec{r}_p \cdot \vec{T}}{|\vec{r}_p| \cdot |\vec{T}|} \quad \cos \gamma_2 = \frac{\vec{r}_p \cdot \vec{T}_o}{|\vec{r}_p| \cdot |\vec{T}_o|}$$

In interval $[0, 360^\circ)$ are 2 solutions for γ_1 and γ_2 . We must always choose the smaller solution.

- a) $\gamma_1 \leq 90^\circ$ and $\gamma_2 \leq 90^\circ$:
 $\Rightarrow \quad \gamma = \gamma_1 \quad \vec{r}$ is between north and east.
- b) $\gamma_1 \leq 90^\circ$ and $\gamma_2 > 90^\circ$:
 $\Rightarrow \quad \gamma = 360^\circ - \gamma_1 \quad \vec{r}$ is between north and west.
- c) $\gamma_1 > 90^\circ$ and $\gamma_2 \leq 90^\circ$:
 $\Rightarrow \quad \gamma = \gamma_1 \quad \vec{r}$ is between east and south.
- d) $\gamma_1 > 90^\circ$ and $\gamma_2 > 90^\circ$:
 $\Rightarrow \quad \gamma = 360^\circ - \gamma_1 \quad \vec{r}$ is between west and south.

The height angle β and the longitude angle γ of $\vec{r}$ are determined. $|\vec{r}|, \gamma, \beta$ are the spherical coordinates on the surface.

$\vec{b}_{ges}$ or the gravitational acceleration $\vec{g}$ of the revolution solid can be transformed for example in this way.

3.2 The ball

We view the situation on a ball:

α = latitude of the ball

Determination of $S(\alpha)$:

$$S(\alpha) = -\tan(90^\circ - \alpha) = -\cot \alpha = \frac{-1}{\tan \alpha}$$

It follows:

$$\vec{n} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi \\ \sin \varphi \\ (-1)^{j-1} \cdot |\tan \alpha| \end{pmatrix} \quad \vec{T} = \begin{pmatrix} (-1)^j \cdot \cos \varphi \\ (-1)^j \cdot \sin \varphi \\ \frac{1}{|\tan \alpha|} \end{pmatrix} \quad \vec{T}_o = \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \varphi \\ \cos \varphi \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Else the calculation is analogous.

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